

Comparison of Water Vapor Measurements by Microwave Radiometers and Raman Lidar

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ABSTRACT

In November-December 1991, a substantial number of remote sensor and *in situ* instruments were operated together in Coffeyville, Kansas, USA, during the climate experiment FIRE II. Included in the suite of instruments were (a) the NOAA Environmental Technology Laboratory's three-channel microwave radiometer (20.6, 31.65, and 90.0 GHz); (b) the NASA/GSFC Raman lidar; and (c) frequent research-quality CLASS radiosondes. The Raman lidar operated only at night and the focus of this portion of the experiment concentrated on clear conditions. The temporal resolution of the Raman lidar was 1 min, the spatial resolution was 75 m, and the upper range of the lidar was about 8.5 km. The lidar data, together with frequent radiosondes and measurements of temperature profiles (every 15 min) by a Radio Acoustic Sounding System (RASS), allowed profiles of temperature and absolute humidity to be estimated every minute. We first present results comparing measurements and calculations of microwave brightness temperature based on three contemporary absorption models. Then, we show comparisons of precipitable water vapor measurements at two-min temporal scales between the two instruments. The results clearly demonstrate the potential of simultaneous operation of radiometers and Raman lidars for fundamental physical studies of water vapor and radiative transfer.

INTRODUCTION

In radiometric remote sensing of the atmosphere, the ability to calculate radiances from underlying state variables is fundamental. For example, to infer temperature and water vapor profiles from satellite measurements, one must be able to calculate radiance emerging from the top of the earth's atmosphere from the underlying profiles of temperature and water vapor. Similar needs occur when measuring precipitable water vapor, integrated cloud liquid, or temperature profiles from ground-based radiometers. Traditionally, such "forward model" calculations have coupled radiosonde observations of the state variables with detailed absorption and radiative transfer models to compare with radiance observations. However, for a variety of reasons, radiosondes are not always satisfactory, especially during low humidity conditions, or when there are large horizontal or temporal gradients in the humidity structure. An alternative method of measuring humidity profiles is that of Raman lidar (England et al., 1992).

In November-December 1991, a substantial number of remote sensor and *in situ* instruments were operated together in Coffeyville, Kansas, USA, during the climate experiment FIRE II. Included in the suite of instruments were (a) the NOAA Environmental Technology Laboratory's (ETL) three-channel microwave radiometer; (b) the NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center's (GSFC) Raman lidar; (c) ETL's Radio Acoustic Sounding System (RASS) and (d) frequent research-quality radiosondes. The Raman lidar operated only at night and our focus was on clear conditions. Here, we present results of simultaneous microwave radiometer measurements with collocated Raman lidar measurements of water vapor. Information on temperature profiles was obtained from composite data from radiosondes and RASS.

DESCRIPTION OF EQUIPMENT

NOAA Transportable Three-Channel Microwave Radiometer

The NOAA system is a three-frequency instrument which is used to measure the column abundances of liquid water in clouds and water vapor in the atmosphere. The system contains three independent microwave radiometers: the first operates at 20.6 GHz and is sensitive primarily to water vapor; the second operates at 31.65 GHz and is sensitive primarily to liquid water; the third operates at 90.0 GHz and is sensitive to both vapor and liquid (Westwater et al., 1990). The total double-sided bandwidth of each receiver is 1 GHz. Another basic feature is that all three channels have the same beamwidth of 2.5° . An important characteristic of the electronics is that the gain is continuously monitored by switching between two reference blackbody loads.

The three radiometers are coupled into an antenna that is steerable in both azimuth and elevation. Here, we use only observations at zenith. The brightness temperatures T_b of the three channels are calibrated by the so-called "tipping curve" calibration procedure, in which measurements of sky brightness temperature as a function of zenith angle are extrapolated to zero air mass. This technique is completely independent of either radiosondes or Raman lidar but does require stratified conditions. An analysis of our tipping curve data (Han et al., 1994) lead to 99% confidence limits for the absolute accuracy of our measurements at 20.6, 31.65, and 90.0 GHz as ± 0.5 , ± 0.9 , and ± 1.4 K. The corresponding rms values for the sensitivities, at our 2-min averaging time, are 0.03, 0.02, and 0.11 K.

Raman Lidar

During the FIRE-II experiment, a new NASA/GSFC Raman water vapor lidar system was deployed (Ferrare et al., 1992). The system uses a XeF laser to transmit light at 351 nm. A telescope collects the combined aerosol and molecular backscattered light at the laser wavelength as well as Raman scattered light from water vapor (403 nm), nitrogen (383 nm), and oxygen (372 nm) molecules. In normal operation data are recorded as one minute profiles with a range resolution of 75 m; the lowest range is 185 m AGL and the upper is nominally about 8.5 km.

Profiles of water vapor mixing ratio are computed from the ratio of the Raman water vapor to Raman nitrogen return signals. The lidar water vapor mixing ratio profiles are calibrated using a weighted least-squares regression of the lidar ratios to the water vapor mixing ratios measured by coincident radiosonde launches. Radiosonde data below 30% relative humidity are not used because of potential unreliable radiosonde moisture measurements in dry conditions (Garland et al., 1992). During the three week FIRE-II experiment period, there were 41 radiosonde humidity profiles used for calibration. A small correction (<7% for altitudes below 12 km) is applied to account for the differential atmospheric transmission between these two Raman wavelengths. Clouds rapidly attenuate the laser beam so that water vapor retrievals are generally limited to altitudes below cloud base. Since the lidar also measures scattering by aerosols and clouds, these cloud base altitudes are easily identified from the lidar data.

RASS

The ETL RASS profiler operated at 404.37 MHz, and reported averaged measurements every 15 minutes. The major characteristics of this transportable instrument, which usually operates in Erie, Colorado, are outlined by Martner et al. (1993). For our purposes, the relevant system parameters are the range resolution of 150 m, the lowest range gate of 350 m, and the maximum upper range, which varied from 1 to 2 km. During the FIRE-II experiment, the upper range was unusually limited due to problems with winds and radio interference.

COMPARISON OF BRIGHTNESS TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS AND CALCULATIONS

Previously, comparisons of measured and calculated T_b 's have been reported (Westwater et al., 1990; England et al., 1993). In these works, clear-sky measurements of zenith T_b were compared with calculations of the Radiative Transfer Equation (RTE) (Westwater, 1993) that are based on atmospheric absorption models. Radiosonde soundings of temperature T , relative humidity RH, and pressure P provided the input profiles to the RTE. Recently, both water vapor and oxygen absorption models have been updated. In this section we compare measurements of T_b 's with calculations based on several models. For convenience we will refer to the models as: RTE76 [Waters (1976) for H_2O , Rosenkranz (1988) for O_2]; RTE87 [Liebe and Layton (1987) for H_2O , Rosenkranz (1988) for O_2]; and RTE93 [Liebe et al. (1993) for H_2O , Liebe et al. (1992) for O_2]. Here, in contrast to previous calculations that were based on radiosondes, we use two-min measurements of water vapor profiles provided by the Raman lidar, together with

temperature profiles provided by RASS and radiosondes. There were a total number of 2506 coincident radiometric and Raman lidar measurements available when there were clear-sky conditions during 10 nights of the experiment. Details of our data-editing procedures are given by Han et al. (1994). The Raman lidar also allowed us to eliminate cloudy data.

In Figure 1, we show typical results of comparing measured and calculated brightness temperatures at 90.0 GHz for a 12 hr time period. Although there is an overall offset between measurements and calculations using RTE76, RTE87 and RTE93, it is encouraging that excellent correlation between measurements is obtained on the finest time scale allowed - two minutes. It is also evident that at 90.0 GHz, the RTE87 model gives the best agreement with measurements. We also show on the figure our estimates of the absolute accuracy in the T_b measurement. A statistical analysis of the entire data set is given by Han et al. (1994). Somewhat surprisingly, no one model was clearly the best at all three frequencies.

Figure 1. Time series of measured and modeled brightness temperatures at 90.0 GHz. Water vapor and temperature profiles taken from the Raman lidar and the RASS are used for the model calculations. Coffeyville, Kansas, November 18, 1991.

COMPARISONS OF PRECIPITABLE WATER VAPOR RETRIEVALS

Precipitable water vapor V (sometimes called columnar integrated water vapor) can be derived directly from the Raman lidar data, given a suitable dry air density profile, and from the radiometer data, by means of a retrieval algorithm. The radiometric retrieval algorithm that we used was the linear statistical method (Westwater, 1993), conditioned on clear sky conditions; all three channels were used in the retrievals. In addition, we removed radiometric - RTE model offsets by adjusting the radiometer T_b data to be consistent with the RTE93 calculations, using rawinsonde data as ground-truth profile data. *A priori* statistics were obtained from Oklahoma City, Oklahoma, a station about 200 km from Coffeyville. We also used coincident rawinsonde data to estimate the non-diagonal covariance matrix of experimental errors S_e .

Figure 2. Time series of precipitable water vapor from the radiometer, Raman lidar and radiosonde. Coffeyville, Kansas, November 18, 1991.

Typical V comparisons are shown in Figure 2, where Raman, microwave, and radiosonde measurements are shown. As is evident, there is excellent correlation on short time scales between Raman and microwave data, and, due to the radiometric offset adjustments, there is only a small bias in V . Note the sometimes poor agreement with rawinsonde measurements, the best agreement being with the CLASS radiosondes. Over a data set of 2506 comparisons, we achieved a rms difference of 0.03 cm. These results should be compared with the values of 0.17 cm (radiometer vs radiosonde) reported by Westwater (1993). The much better agreement between Raman and radiometer arises from at least four reasons: (a) the remote sensors are both simultaneously viewing the same zenith direction, although with different beamwidths (Raman beamwidth = 0.5×0.7 mrad, microwave beamwidths $\approx 2.5^\circ = 43.6$ mrad); (b) these data are confined to clear sky conditions, and the radiometer retrieval coefficients are determined for these conditions; (c) three, rather than two, channels were used in the radiometric retrievals; and (d) a non-diagonal experimentally-determined error covariance matrix S_e was used in the construction of retrieval coefficients.

We also compared power spectra of V as determined by the two remote measurements and for a 3-hr portion of the time period shown in Figure 2. For our data, taken with two-min averaging times, the Nyquist frequency was 15 cycles/hr. For the computation of spectra, we used a spectral-windowing method that uses the spectral window of Parzen (Jenkins and Watts, 1969) with a maximum lag of 44 min. A typical example of the spectra is shown in Figure 3. For comparison, we have plotted a line with a $-5/3$ slope that would represent, for a constant wind, the spectral decay of a single level of isotropic homogeneous turbulence. As would be expected from the time series shown in Figure 2, the spectra are also in reasonable agreement.

Figure 3. Spectra of precipitable water vapor from the radiometer and the Raman Lidar. Coffeyville, Kansas, November 18, 1991.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of Raman lidar data for the detailed studies of tropospheric water vapor absorption and emission has significant potential. The vertical resolution of 75 m and the temporal resolution of 1 min have significant advantages over radiosondes which frequently are displaced from a radiometer's observing volume and which take about 30 min to traverse the major portion of the water vapor overburden. Another advantage is that the lidar can indicate the presence or absence of clouds, so that clear-sky radiative transfer calculations can be made confidently. On the negative side, the Raman soundings reach to ≈ 8.5 km altitudes only during the night, and the lidar usually does not penetrate clouds.

We have examined three absorption models here. At the lower frequencies of 20.6 and 31.65 GHz and for the relatively dry Coffeyville, Kansas, environment, the calculations based on RTE76 and RTE93 produced similar results, with rms differences between measurements and calculations of ≈ 0.5 K. However, the results at 90 GHz using RTE93 were not substantially better than the earlier RTE87, and may be worse. It was previously established that RTE76 poorly modeled 90 GHz emission. Since 90 GHz emission is not affected by changes in the 22.235 water vapor line parameters, the differences could be due to changes in the parameterization of the water vapor continuum or also in the description of the O_2 far wing behavior. We plan to use this data set to derive our own absorption parameters. Definitive experiments using collocated Raman lidar and microwave radiometers could be conducted in a variety of humidity climatologies to provide a rich data base for absorption and emission studies.

The ability to calculate downward radiances in spectral regions of low atmospheric transmission is also important for the microwave remote sensing of moisture from satellites (Alishouse et al., 1990a; Alishouse et al., 1990b), since the downward flowing atmospheric radiance closely approximates

the upward flowing atmospheric radiance. Although satellite retrievals of moisture and cloud liquid are also affected by variations in surface emissivity, better atmospheric absorption models are still fundamental to improved satellite retrievals. In addition, satellite flights over suitably located Raman lidar and microwave radiometers could prove very useful for improvements in satellite data validation and product improvement. For example, if these upward-looking microwave radiometers had frequencies that coincided with, say, DMSP/SSM/I channels, a rich variety of data sets could be obtained.

The excellent temporal correlations between the Raman lidar's and the microwave radiometer's determination of precipitable water vapor confirms the ability of both of the instruments to follow rapid changes in moisture. The already demonstrated agreement in profile determination between the Raman lidar and radiosondes lends further confirmation to this instrument's ability as a meteorological research tool and as ground truth for passive remote sensors.

Acknowledgements: The authors thank Dr. H. J. Liebe for providing us with copies of his latest MPM software, as well as discussing several aspects of his work. The authors also thank Dr. R. G. Strauch, K. Moran, and D. Wertz for providing their interpolated RASS and rawinsonde data. This work was partially supported by the Department of Energy's Atmospheric Radiation Measurements Program.

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